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The UPSKILLS game preferences survey

UPSKILLS Intellectual output 4.1

Compiled by:
Vanessa Camilleri

* University of Malta

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Executive Summary

This report describes the ‘Game Preferences Survey’ which has been specifically designed for the UPSKILLS target audience to provide a means of understanding the types of games the project stakeholders favour, so as to identify the games best adapted to their needs. This survey used a tool that comprises of a questionnaire having 14 items. Analysis has been carried out in terms of demographic values as well as percentage scores for each item. The results indicated that a substantial number of respondents who play games, prefer playing games alone in the comfort of their homes, using either the PC or a mobile device, for leisure. From the results it can also be inferred that a significant amount of the representative group of the UPSKILLS audience do not play games for a lengthy period of time, but prefer games to be short, not complex, engaging and with a good narrative. These results were used to look for specific characteristics when adapting or identifying games that are appropriate and fall within the scope of the UPSKILLS project.

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1. Introduction

This report describes the user preference survey that was conducted with a target sample of students on linguistics and language-related courses to determine if they played games, and if yes, which genre or type of games do they play. This survey aimed to obtain an overall perspective of the needs of the target project audience so as to ensure that the games suggested within the UPSKILLS project would align to their preferences.

2. Game preferences survey

2.1 Rationale

It is often assumed that young people are avid gamers. It may also be sometimes assumed that all games can lead to a more effective learning if applied to the education context. This may not always be the case and may lead to an erroneous judgement when choosing which games are best adapted to a specific education scenario. A game preferences survey was specifically designed for UPSKILLS to shed some light and gain insights into the trends and the choices of game play by the project target group, undergraduate and postgraduate students following courses in language studies and linguistics. The aim of the intellectual output that is responsible for designing and exploiting digital games is that of offering an alternative way of learning, that fits in with the target stakeholder preferences. Therefore the results from this survey are important to provide a guide into the games which will be most preferred by the stakeholders in such a way as to facilitate and support the acceptance and adoption of the chosen games and methods of play.

2.2 Methodology

The questionnaire tool is designed in a way as to elicit clear and unambiguous responses from the user group. Although the first set of questions centre around demographic information, the rest of the questions are close-ended questions, with the last 2 questions that allow for multiple responses and one that uses the 5-point Likert scale to determine the attitudes and opinions of the participants about game play. The survey questions were purposely designed close-ended to get as higher a response rate as possible by the users whilst at the same time guiding the respondents' answers when it comes to game play preferences. The final question is reserved as an open-ended question to gain further insights into the participants' perceptions about what makes a game complex. The aim of this question is to identify game characteristics which the user group might be less willing to accept and adopt on the basis of complexity in learning the rules of the game or playing it.

2.2.1 Participants

The participants for this survey were chosen on the basis of the target user group for the UPSKILLS project. All project partners were invited to distribute the online questionnaire to their student groups with a special interest in linguistics and language technology with a background and context similar to the project stakeholders. Participants voluntarily signed up to answer the questionnaire items. In all 215 responses were recorded.

2.2.2 Testing and validation

A pre-testing exercise was carried out prior to the distribution of the questionnaire with the aim of checking whether the questions have been framed properly, thus producing the desired results. Question order as well as clarity of the wording used were also checked, to ensure the effectiveness of the methodology used. The pre-testing was carried out amongst the UPSKILLS project partners and the items in the questionnaire tested for clarity, order and language.

In parallel, content and face validity tests of the questionnaire were also done with experts in the field of games and game research to understand whether the responses reflect the needs and the scope of the project. In the face validity exercise each question was discussed at length with an expert to understand how the answers could be used to gain insights into game preferences. Some issues were resolved including by changing item response type.

2.3 Results

In total 215 responses were received. 62 (28.8%) of the respondents declared they did not play any games.

In terms of demographics the participants were mostly female (167 - 77.7%) and in the 18-24 age category (162 - 75.3%). 105 from 215 participants were from Italy, while the rest were divided between Serbia, Switzerland, and a number of European countries.

Figure 1. Gender demographics and age of respondents

2.3.1 Game play

Out of 164 responses, 35% of the respondents claim that they play 1-3 hours a week, confirming their status as occasional gamers, whereas 20.3% claim they play 4-8 hours a week. A further 23.4% claim they don't play games every week. Around 20% of the respondents claim they play for more than 9 hours per week.

164 responses were recorded for the question regarding the time spent playing. On average 62% claim they play 30mins - 1 hour or less whilst 32% of the respondents mention that they spent between 1-3 hours of game play.

Figure 2. Length of time spent playing per session

An overwhelming majority, approximately 74%, when asked where they tend to play games claim that they only play games at home (during the day as well as during the night) whilst only approximately 20% claim they play whilst commuting, using their mobile phone.

Figure 3. Location of play

The question which follows asks the participants what device they prefer to play on, and 50% of the respondents chose the mobile phone/tablet. 42% claim they play games using their PC. 42% of the respondents also claim they prefer physical board games.

Figure 4. Game-playing devices

The game genre which is the most popular with the participants is the adventure genre, which is followed closely by role-playing, strategy, board, as well as card games.

Figure 5. Preferred game genres

161 respondents answered the question about the length of time they usually spend playing one game. 74 respondents (46%) replied that they tend to play a game for approximately 2 months, while 21% of the respondents answered that they tend to play a game for up to 1 month. Approximately 20% responded that they prefer to play games for a shorter span of time - between 1-2 weeks.

Figure 6. Length of game play per game

57.8% of the participants declared that they prefer to play alone rather than in a team, whilst 24% claim that they prefer playing when teaming up with others. A further 11% like to play player vs. player games. Other respondents did not have specific preferences but claimed they could play either alone or with friends.

Figure 7. Personal game play preference

This question allowed for multiple responses by the participants. The majority agree that they play mostly for leisure (85%) whilst a number of them play as a distraction to kill time (46%) and as a social activity (32.5%). Interestingly 21.5% of the respondents claim they play to learn (using simulation/training games).

Figure 8. Reason for playing games

The following question uses a 5-point Likert scale question to determine the self-perception of the respondents in relation to their gaming preferences, abilities, and beliefs regarding games. A total of 163 respondents answered this question. From the 163 respondents, only 39 think of themselves as gamers whilst 65 respondents think that some of the games are too complicated.

Only 22 like watching eSports (a category of video games that includes spectators) whilst 33 carry no opinion about watching e-Sports.

93 respondents attribute their introduction to games to their friends. 82 respondents play mobile games and claim that it is just as fun as playing console games. 60 respondents have no opinion on whether social media are good sources of information on games. 73 respondents believe that the best games are free whilst 47 respondents disagree with this claim. Only 53 respondents prefer to team up with friends when playing. A majority of 111 respondents prefer to play games that have an exciting narrative, whilst 56 like to play puzzle games. 57 respondents have no opinion about whether they prefer to play games outdoors, whilst only 32 like to play games where they have to be physically active. 149 respondents agree that playing games can lead to a form of learning. 144 respondents agree that games provide a good distraction from stress. 73 respondents agree that games can be used during their coursework, whilst 56 hold no preference over the use of games during the coursework.

The last question of the survey asked the respondents about their personal opinions regarding game complexity and what makes a game complicated.

In general, the respondents indicated a number of characteristics that made games more complex to play:

- Significant motor-sight co-ordination; this increases the amount of effort involved in game play that would reduce its leisure or stress relieving component;
- Significant mental/cognitive workload leading to player frustration;
- Lengthy instructions accompanying a game that requires a considerable amount of time to play;
- A steep learning curve to the game rules and game dynamics.

2.4 Discussion of results

The results from this survey (Question 4) indicate that contrary to popular perception, there are a number of respondents among the target project stakeholders, who do not consider themselves as gamers. In addition the indications are that the majority of respondents would not take much time playing. This suggests a type of player who spends on average a couple of months playing one game before moving on to another, whilst spending a few minutes to an hour for each game session. Results also indicate that the target respondents prefer to play alone at home possibly using a mobile device.

In terms of game characteristics, the respondents indicate that they prefer an engaging and interesting narrative for their game play. There are also indications that strategy, adventure and role playing games are amongst the game genres which would be more popular. In relation to game genres, some respondents indicated that puzzle games might be more complex and thus may be quite frustrating to play. Interestingly respondents indicated their preference for board and card games, thus suggesting possibilities of adopting games other than digital or video games.

Other complexity factors that may influence the target audience's choice of which games to play or not, include lengthy instructions or a steep learning curve. Respondents indicated that e-Sports as well as games that may involve a degree of physical activity as well as those requiring a substantial amount of hand-eye co-ordination may prove to be quite challenging for them in terms of physical effort involved. In fact only 32 out of 163 respondents indicated that they prefer to be physically active whilst playing games. Team games also do not seem to be very popular, with 58% of the respondents, showing their preference for solo play.

Most of the respondents agreed that they play games for leisure, to de-stress, and kill time. This would suggest a type of person who does not like overly complicated, lengthy games, but games which are engaging, light and fun to play.

Following these results, it seems that for the chosen representative target audience of students in linguistics and languages, focusing on games and gamification may not be their priority. However, for those students who enjoy playing, they would tend to enjoy playing games that are simple, short, have an engaging narrative, and can be conducive to some form of learning. Those games that tend toward complexity or physical action, would not be amongst the preferred choice of games of the UPSKILLS target audience.

Annex 1 – Game Play Preferences Questionnaire

The UPSKILLS project is an Erasmus+ strategic partnership for higher education that seeks to identify and tackle the gaps and mismatches in digital skills for linguistics and language students through the development of a new curriculum component and supporting materials to be embedded in existing programmes of study. To this end, we are investigating the use of games and gamification as supporting methods to target skills gaps and address industry and societal needs.

This survey is being used as part of data collection for this strand of the UPSKILLS project. It is aimed towards current and prospective students as well as recent graduates of degree in languages and linguistics. It should not take more than 5-10 minutes to complete.

Further information about the project can be found at <https://upskillsproject.eu/>. If you have questions about this survey, please contact Dr Vanessa Camilleri from the University of Malta at vanessa.camilleri@um.edu.mt.

The information provided by you in this questionnaire will be used for research purposes. It will not be used in a manner which would allow the identification of your individual responses. Anonymised research data will be archived in order to make it available to other researchers in UPSKILLS in line with current data sharing practices.

1. Gender *

*Required

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

2. Age *

- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- Above 65

3. Country of Residence *

- Austria
- Croatia
- Italy
- Malta
- Serbia

Switzerland

Other:

4. Do you play games? *

Yes

No - if you answered No, then you can proceed to click Next and submit the form.

Game play

5. How many hours a week do you play?

1-3 hours/week

4-8 hours/week

9-14 hours/week

15-21hours/week

21+ hours/week

I don't play games every week

6. For any one game session, how long on average do you spend playing?

30mins or less 30mins

1hour

1-3 hours

3-5 hours

5+ hours

7. Where do you typically play?

At home, during the day At home, during the night

At university/work/institute

On the mobile phone, whilst commuting/waiting for classes/during lunch break

Outdoors with friends

Other:

8. What do you prefer to play games on? (*Tick all that apply.*)

Consoles (Playstation 4/5, XBox, Wii, etc.)

PC (Purchased/downloaded games, Online games, etc.)

Handheld Console (Nintendo Switch, etc)

Mobile Phone/Tablet Physical Board/card game

9. What genre of games do you most frequently like to play? (*Tick all that apply.*)

Action

- Adventure
- Arcade
- Board
- Card
- Massively Multiplayer Online Role Playing Games (MMORPG)
- Mystery
- Puzzle
- Role-playing Games (RPG) Sports
- Strategy
- Other:

10. How long do you usually play one game for?

- Less than 1 week Up to 2 weeks
- Up to 1 month Up to 2 months
- More than 2 months

11. How do you prefer to play games?

- Alone
- Teaming with others
- Player vs. Player
- Other:

12. Why do you play games? (*Tick all that apply.*)

- Social activity
- For leisure
- Personal accomplishment
- Distraction to kill time
- For a prize/reward
- To learn (can apply to specific training/simulation games)
- Other:

13. (*Mark only one oval per row*)

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I think of myself as a gamer					
Some of the games are too complicated					

I enjoy watching eSports					
I started to play certain games because my friends were also playing them					
Playing mobile games (smartphone, tablet) can be as much fun as playing console or PC games.					
Social media (Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram) are important sources of information on games					
Some of the best games are free					
I prefer to play games which involve teaming up with friends					
I tend to play games that have an engaging narrative/plot					
I prefer to play puzzle games					
I enjoy playing games that are played outdoors					
I prefer to be physically active whilst playing games					
I believe that playing games does not lead to any form of learning					
Playing games is good as a distraction from stress					
I don't agree with using games during my coursework					

14. If you have answered that you think some of the games are too complicated, can you please mention a few of those games and what, in your opinion, makes them complicated?